

COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF A
VILLAGE IN BANGLADESH.

Author:

Md Akash
Department of Public Administration
University of Dhaka

Introduction

The term "rural development" is made up of the phrases "rural" and "development." The term "rural" denotes a remote and secluded place that is inferior to urban areas and lacks modern amenities. The majority of its residents work in agriculture. Rural areas have limited educational opportunities, restricted job opportunities, and a heavy reliance on natural resources, among other things. The other half of the word, development, denotes a multi-faceted idea. It entails constructive development in all sectors, including agriculture, industry, culture, economics, technology, health and nutrition, education, human resources, and the environment. Agricultural development, economic development, technical development, socio-cultural development, institutional development, educational development, and political development are all part of the process of improving the quality of life and economic wellbeing of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas.

In this paper, I shall describe the village of Chachai's overall development. Aside from that, I'll talk about some of the challenges and neglected projects in this village that need to be developed.

Overview of Chachai village:

Chachai is the name of my village. It is located in Union No. 6, which is part of the Lohagara Police Station in the Narail District of the Khulna Division. A primary school, a lower secondary school, a post office, three madrasas, and thirteen mosques are located in the settlement. A community clinic is also available.

The village has an all-electric power system. Every home in this area is wired for power. A paved road and a brick road running through the settlement. The village now has internet access, and the village's post office and school have been upgraded to modern high-speed

internet connections. Various farms in the village are receiving financial aid. Several farmers have recently received cash help of 10,000 takas. The Ministry of Disaster and Relief offered a family in this village a house with a top veranda, 2 rooms, 1 kitchen, and 1 bathroom in 2020. Solar electricity of 60 watts has also been given.

Local government services in the development of Chachai village:

Poverty reduction, agricultural development, health care, electrification, and other methods in which the government is attempting to develop this village. The village has 315 poor families, according to the Jaipur Union Digital Center. Significant services are among the government's continued efforts to relieve poverty by providing a variety of services to these extremely impoverished families.

1. VGF Card
2. Widows Allowance
3. VGD Card
4. Old Age Allowance
5. Protibandhi student Allowance
6. Ektee Bari Ektee khamar
7. Kormosuci Card
8. Krisi Card
9. Mothers Card

Overview of services

1. VGF Card:

The operation of vulnerable group feeding is referred to as VGF. Each family that receives a VGF card can buy rice from government officials for a fixed monthly price of 10 takas per kg. According to statistics from the 6 No Jaipur Union Digital Center, Chachai Purbapara has 200 VGF cardholders, while Chachai Paschimpara has 167 VGF cardholders. In Chachai village, there are a total of 367 VGF cardholders. They can afford to buy rice at a modest price and feed their families¹.

2. Widows Allowance:

Under the Widows and Husbands Abuse Women Allowance Program, "widow" refers to those whose spouses have died; "husband abuse" refers to those who have been divorced by their husbands or have lived together for at least two years for any other reason. In the fiscal year 2020-21, a total of Tk 1230 crore has been budgeted for 20 lakh 50 thousand recipients at a cost of Tk 500 per person per month under this program². The allowance is distributed to all recipients by opening a bank account in their name for TK 10. Widows and abusive women receive financial aid for socioeconomic growth and social security, as well as to improve their status in the family and community, as well as to improve their medical treatment and nourishment. A total of 45 widows from Chachai village received widow allowance, according to the Union Digital Center³.

3. VGD Card:

The VGD program, run by the Ministry of Women and Children Affairs, is one of the social security programs in Bangladesh aimed at improving the socioeconomic position of rural poor women. It aims to improve the living conditions of completely disadvantaged households, particularly women. VGD beneficiaries receive 30 kilograms of packaged food (rice) every month, as well as training from contracted NGOs. In Chachai village, 68 women benefit from the VGD program⁴.

4. Old Age Allowance:

The aged, impoverished, low-income, or ineligible elderly people of the country receive 500 takas per month for the objective of providing social security and boosting their position in the family and society. In 2013, the age of women was reduced from 65 to 72 years to incorporate more women in the allowance program⁵. Chachai village has a total of 21 senior recipients⁶.

5. Protibandhi student Allowance:

Disability allowances are provided by the government to assist students with disabilities in obtaining an education. According to the Jaipur Union Digital Center, this stipend was given to 11 physically and visually handicapped children in Chachai village⁷.

6. Ektee Bari Ektee khamar.

Bangladesh's government must construct Ektee Bari Ektee khamar for every family. Following this, the Ektee Bari Ektee khamar program was launched in all Bangladeshi districts, Upazilas, and unions.

This project is also in Chachai village in Narail District's Jaipur Union of Lohagara Upazila. Poor households in this union can alleviate their poverty by taking out low-interest loans under this program.

7. Kormosuci Card:

This project has encompassed the underprivileged and indigent families of Chachai village. This task has been delegated to the family's female members. Every month, everyone who works is paid. Their job included repairing village roads, cleaning roadside areas, planting grass along with roadside areas, planting trees, and caring for the trees.

8. Krisi Card:

The local administration is attempting to improve the farmers' socioeconomic situation and increase crop production in Chachai village. Agricultural meetings involving all farmers are held as part of this effort. Farmers are taught contemporary producing methods. Seeds of new types are distributed, as well as nutrients. Modern agricultural technology, such as tractors and threshing machines, are available in the village. All of this equipment was distributed to about 15 families in Chachai village. All of these machines are used in production by a few farming households.

9. Mothers Card:

Under this scheme, all moms in Chachai village receive government help during their pregnancy. During this time, the government supplies food to suit the mother's and baby's nutritional needs. The government is giving a variety of chances for this village's socio-economic growth. People's socioeconomic and social growth is being attained, and the government's goals are being implemented.

Apart from these, Chachai village has certain issues that require development and reform, like as

1. Drug problem
2. Need to Reconstruct bridge
3. Need to dig canals

Overview of the problems

1. Drug Problem:

Drug addiction is one of the most serious issues in Chachai village. In this village, drugs are freely bought and sold. This medicine is being used by powerful people in the village. As a result, the medicine supply remains unaffected. There is no obvious activity of the local government system in this scenario. The Upazila police have taken no action. To remove drug addiction, extensive education efforts should be implemented in the area. The dangers of drugs must be made known to influential people. Everyone in the village has to be aware of how drug addiction is ruining the village's youth. Those who buy and sell drugs should face legal consequences. Everyone in the village should be taught to abstain from using drugs. In the rural schools, anti-drug meetings and rallies should be arranged. Drugs are lethal. Using drugs results in the death of one's life. In the family, there is a schism. Cancer can be caused by drug misuse. The baby is gasping for air. These must be spread across the villages. Not to mention drugs, everyone in the hamlet should be familiar with the motto "drugs kill."

2. Need to Reconstruct bridge

Just west of Chachai village is a bridge. This bridge connects two communities. During the monsoon season, water from around 5 acres of land in Chachai village is diverted to the canal via this bridge. In the year 2019, the bridge collapsed. However, the bridge has yet to be constructed. This bridge must be constructed quickly. This has been communicated to the chairman of the local government system. In the last two years, however, no action has been made.

3. Need to dig canals

In Chachai village, there are two waterways. Two waterways are filled during the monsoon season. The residents of the community go fishing from this location. The water in these two canals, on the other hand, lasts for 5-6 months. Every year, the canal dries up between January and February. Two canals need to be dug, although neither has been dug in the last 30 years or so. Because the canal's depth and water holding capacity have both reduced, this is the case. Crop fields can be found on both sides of the canal. As a result, having a water supply in the two canals is critical. This canal is devoid of fish, and every year, jute is soaked in the canal water. The local authority has taken no effort too far to excavate these two canals in Chachai village.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

The overall development of the village is going on. Yet there are some problems. Most of the services provided by the local government are received by the relatives of the people working in the local government. The fact is that the poor get very little access to these services. There is also no education system for the illiterate and the elderly in the village. There is a need to raise awareness in the villages, the people of the villages still resort to modern medicine instead of scrubbing. Adult education should be started in the village, for this night education should be introduced with the help of village school teachers. All the modern types of equipment provided by the government for agricultural work are being taken over by the influential people of the village, who are selling this equipment to others if they do not need them, but those who were able to use this equipment are being deprived of using them. There are still factions in the village, with little fighting between one faction and the other. The administration plays a puppet role in this. There is no way they can stop all these fights. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure accountability in all the activities of the local government and to ensure that every beneficiary receives the services properly. The people of the village need to be informed about the services provided by the government. Those who are poor in the village, those who deserve all these benefits from the government have to provide services. Then it will be possible to implement all the steps taken by the central government for the development of the village and the village will be developed.

REFERENCE:

1. Joypur Union. (n.d.). Retrieved July 27, 2021, from <http://joypurup.narail.gov.bd/site/page/f3c258fa-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766/http%3A%2F%2Fjoypurup.narail.gov.bd%2Fsite%2Fpage%2Ff3c258fa-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766%2F%25E0%25A6%25AD%25E0%25A6%25BF%25E0%25A6%259C%25E0%25A6%25BF%25E0%25A6%258F%25E0%25A6%25AB>
2. Ministry of Social Welfare. (n.d.). Retrieved Jun 21, 2021, from <https://msw.gov.bd/site/page/Widow-Allowances>
3. Joypur Union. (n.d.). Retrieved July 27, 2021, from <http://joypurup.narail.gov.bd/site/page/f3dc7ebe-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766/%E0%A6%AC%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%A7%E0%A6%AC%E0%A6%BE%20%E0%A6%AD%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%A4%E0%A6%BE>
4. Joypur Union. (n.d.). Retrieved July 27, 2021, from <http://joypurup.narail.gov.bd/site/page/f3dc6855-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766/http%3A%2F%2Fjoypurup.narail.gov.bd%2Fsite%2Fpage%2Ff3dc6855-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766%2F%25E0%25A6%25AD%25E0%25A6%25BF%25E0%25A6%259C%25E0%25A6%25BF%25E0%25A6%25A1%25E0%25A6%25BF>
5. Department of Social Services. (n.d.). Retrieved Jun 21, 2021, from <http://www.dss.gov.bd/site/page/Old-Age-Allowance>
6. Joypur Union. (n.d.). Retrieved July 27, 2021, from <http://joypurup.narail.gov.bd/site/page/f3dcb70a-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766/http%3A%2F%2Fjoypurup.narail.gov.bd%2Fsite%2Fpage%2Ff3dcb70a-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766%2F%25E0%25A6%25AC%25E0%25A6%25AF%25E0%25A6%25BC%25E0%25A6%25B8%25E0%25A7%258D%25E0%25A6%2595%2520%25E0%25A6%25AD%25E0%25A6%25BE%25E0%25A6%25A4%25E0%25A6%25BE>
7. Joypur Union. (n.d.). Retrieved July 27, 2021, from <http://joypurup.narail.gov.bd/site/page/f3dcfb43-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766/http%3A%2F%2Fjoypurup.narail.gov.bd%2Fsite%2Fpage%2Ff3dcfb43-1c4a-11e7-8f57-286ed488c766%2F%25E0%25A6%25AA%25E0%25A7%258D%25E0%25A6%25B0%25E0%25A6%25A4%25E0%25A6%25BF%25E0%25A6%25AC%25E0%25A6%25A8%25E0%25A7%258D%25E0%25A6%25A7%25E0%25A7%2580%2520%25E0%25A6%259B%25E0%25A6%25BE%25E0%25A6%25A4%25E0%25A7%258D%25E0%25A6%25B0-%25E0%25A6%259B%25E0%25A6%25BE%25E0%25A6%25A4%25E0%25A7%258D%25E0%25A6%25B0%25E0%25A7%2580%2520%25E0%25A6%25AD%25E0%25A6%25BE%25E0%25A6%25A4%25E0%25A6%25BE>